

Table 2. Effect of a 10-day 12°C water treatment 10 days after sowing on the growth duration of 2 rice varieties. IRRI, 1980.

Observation	IR22553		IR20654	
	Plants (no.)	% of the population	Plants (no.)	% of the population
Delayed flowering	203	46	362	38
Same flowering duration	103	23	307	32
Early flowering	73	17	137	14
Dead	63	14	148	16
Total number tested	442		954	

crosses studied (Table 2). Some lines, however, actually headed earlier as a result of the treatment. Since the plants are still segregating, it is not possible to definitely say that the treatment caused earliness or delay in heading.

In general, the plants damaged severely

by the cold water treatment showed greater delay in heading (Table 3). In both crosses, the difference in average flowering date between the treated plants and the control is small for plants with a score of 1 to 3. Screening for cold tolerance at the seedling stage can be

Table 3. Effect of 10-day 12°C water treatment 10 days after sowing on the yellowing of leaves of 2 rice varieties. IRRI, 1980.

Score	F ₃ plants ^a (no.)	
	IR22553	IR20654
1-3	17 (+5)	129 (+3)
Green		
5	39 (+5)	261 (+9)
Light green		
7-9	386 (+6)	564 (+8)
Yellow - dead		
Total	442	954

^aFigures inside the parentheses show the average number of days heading was delayed.

conducted during the RGA of F₃ plants without any great delay in heading of the tolerant lines. ■

Pest management and control DISEASES

Yellow wilt of rice in the lower Amazon Basin, Brazil

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The yellow wilt problem of rice was noted in a few mechanically cultivated fields of irrigated rice in the lower Amazon Basin in the second crop season of 1978. The disorder became more serious in the first and second crop seasons of 1979 on IR22 in the varzea marshland soils.

The rice plant's growth usually proceeded normally until 1 or 2 weeks before the flowering-milk stages; then the older leaves began to die rapidly and the younger leaves turned yellow brown and gradually died back from the tips. About 1 or 2 weeks before harvest, the yellow-brown leaves suddenly withered. Ripening was accelerated and at harvest the affected plants looked dehydrated, dirty, weak, and droopy; and had no green or light-yellow leaves.

Such crops had many decayed and dead roots and were usually attacked by *Helminthosporium* leaf spot, *Cercospora* leaf spot, *Pyricularia* neck blast, or *Rhizoctonia* sheath blight, or two or more of the diseases. But such attacks appeared secondary. Yields were low

because of the low photosynthetic activity of the leaves and the poor root systems. The appropriate harvest time was difficult to determine because the leaves dried and died before maturation, and the same panicles contained green as well as ripe grains. Grain quality was usually poor. In cases where the disorder occurred before flowering, plant growth was poor. A yellow-brown discoloration appeared on the tips of green leaves, and the older leaves dried and died, starting from the tips. At flowering the panicles varied in height and few leaves remained green. Leaves then withered more rapidly. Drainage for harvesting accelerated the withering. The symptoms usually occurred on plants grown in soils of low organic matter. The name *yellow wilt* was used because of the yellowing and wilting symptoms.

A combination of factors including iron toxicity, potassium deficiency, and disease incidence was suspected to cause yellow wilt. Recent studies show that the yellow wilt disorder is associated with potassium deficiency in the soil solution and low potassium content of the plants.

Increasing the supply of potassium fertilizer from the previous recommendation of 20-30 kg/ha to 70-90 kg/ha and

split application of potassium noticeably alleviated the disorder.

Three tentative remedies have been recommended:

1. submergence of the varzea marshland soils for at least 1 month before planting;
2. increase in potassium fertilizer up to 70-90 kg/ha and splitting its application; and
3. application of higher levels of potassium fertilizer, but avoidance of excessive nitrogen dressing, at about the maximum-tillering stage. ■

Experimental observations on rice sheath rot disease

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Semidwarf rice cultivars are often susceptible to sheath rot disease caused by *Acrocyndrium oryzae*, but tall cultivars are relatively resistant. Therefore research was conducted to determine if the semidwarfs' susceptibility could be altered by use of a growth substance to change the host plants' growth pattern.

Two consecutive foliar sprays of gibberellic acid (GA, 100 µg/ml) applied

at 7 and 3 days before inoculation (by the method of Purkayastha and Ray Chaudhuri) to 9-week-old semidwarfs Jaya and TN1 significantly reduced sheath rot disease. The treatment also increased plant height. For Jaya, the control was 54.6 cm high; the plant with 100 ppm GA was 83.8 cm. For TN1, the control was 57.2 cm; the plant with 100 ppm GA was 76.7 cm. The length of internodes also increased (Jaya: 7.1 cm for the control, 12.9 cm with 100 ppm GA; TN1: 6.4 cm for the control, 10.81 cm with 100 ppm GA). Low concentrations of GA stimulated mycelial growth (increase of 11.44% with 0.1 µg/ml and 4.8% with 1 µg/ml); higher concentrations (10 and 100 µg/ml) inhibited growth (4.5% and 9.3% reduction, respectively) of the pathogen *in vitro*. Although 100 ppm GA inhibited

pathogen growth and decreased disease intensity considerably, it is not clear whether that was a direct effect of GA on the pathogen within the host tissue or was due to changes induced by GA in the plants' growth pattern. Amin and associates pointed out in 1974 that dwarf cultivars were prone to sheath rot probably because of their short internodes. Treatment of noninoculated (healthy) leaf sheaths with GA (100 µg/ml) initially enhanced the amino acid level (Jaya, 7.6%; TN1, 9.3% increase in relation to untreated, non-inoculated control) but decreased it considerably 7 days after inoculation of untreated plants (Jaya, 29.4%; TN1, 32.3% decrease in relation to untreated, non-inoculated control, on the basis of detected amino acids and amides). In the case of GA-treated plants, the amino

acid level also decreased 7 days after inoculation (Jaya, 19.3%; TN1, 23.1%).

The amino acids and amides were estimated by the method described by Purkayastha and Mukhopadhyay in 1976. In addition, total phenol contents of leaf sheaths were measured by the method of Folin-Denis. Colorimetric studies revealed that total phenol levels were markedly higher in untreated infected leaf sheaths (by 145.9% in Jaya and by 126.7% in TN1) than in the control and slightly after GA (100 µg/ml) treatment. But ferulic acid significantly increased in treated leaf sheaths. The application of GA may cause biochemical changes in host plants, but it undoubtedly creates a condition unfavorable for the growth of invading parasites. ■

Effect of chemicals on parasitic nematode populations and yields in continuously cropped uplands

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After monitoring nematode populations at Makassa, the upland experimental site of the Rokupr Rice Research Station, a progressive buildup of parasitic nematode populations was noted. In the 1979 cropping season, the 6th successive year that the site was planted to rice, the number of plant parasitic nematodes averaged 1,034/100 cc of rhizospheric soil among plots planted to cultivar TOX502-13-SLR. The recovered nematodes and their relative proportions were *Pratylenchus* sp., 2%; *Helicotylenchus* sp., 25%; *Criconemoides* sp., 21%; *Tylenchus* sp., 16%; *Rotylenchulus* sp., 5%; and *Aphelenchus* sp., 4%. The corresponding figure per 10-g root sample was 219, distributed as follows: *Pratylenchus*, 34%; *Helicotylenchus* sp., 32%; and *Criconemoides*, 34%.

A study to determine the effects of DD, Mocap, and carbofuran on nematode populations and yields was conducted in the 1979 season. DD was applied by pouring a measured quantity into

Table 1. Number of plant parasite nematodes in rhizospheric soil and roots at harvest, Sierra Leone.

Treatment	Application	Plant parasitic nematodes (no./100 cc rhizospheric soil)		Plant parasitic nematodes (no./10-g root)	
		TOX502-13-SLR	LAC23	TOX502-13-SLR	LAC23
Control	—	1034	710	219	188
DD	303 liters/ha	689	460	123	102
Mocap	56 kg/ha	597	542	132	106
Carbofuran	31 kg/ha	653	494	120	101
LSD (0.05)		176	49.6	27.4	28.5
CV (%)		14.9	3.2	11.6	11.4

previously prepared holes, 20–30cm deep and 15 cm apart, 2 weeks before seeding. A 1:2 Mocap-sand mixture was prepared and broadcast evenly before sowing. Carbofuran granules, also applied before sowing, were broadcast evenly without mixing with sand.

The cultivars LAC23 and TOX502-13-SLR were used separately. Plots were laid in a randomized complete block design with four replications. The plants were raised following recommended cultural and management practices.

At harvest, the nematode populations in rhizospheric soil and on roots were determined.

All three chemicals significantly reduced parasitic nematode populations in rhizospheric soil and in the roots of both cultivars (Table 1). More nematodes were recovered from the rhizospheric soil than from the roots. All chemicals

Table 2. Grain yield of two cultivars, Sierra Leone.

Treatment	Yield (t/ha)	
	TOX502-13-SLR	LAC23
Control	1.4	1.9
DD	2.5	3.6
Mocap	2.1	2.4
Furadan	2.2	2.8
LSD (0.05)	0.5	1.1
CV (%)	16.5	26.5

significantly increased the yields of TOX502-13-SLR, but only DD significantly increased the yields of LAC23 (Table 2). ■

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